

From Cloudiness to Clarity: Predictive Modeling for Early Diagnosis of Peritonitis in Peritoneal Dialysis (CLEAR-PD)

Version 1

Description

Peritonitis is one of the most serious complications of peritoneal dialysis (PD), potentially leading to hospitalization, catheter loss, or even death. Currently, one of the cornerstone diagnostic methods relies on the visual inspection of dialysate turbidity, which is subjective and may delay the initiation of timely treatment. The aim of this project is to develop innovative, patient-friendly tools for the early detection of PD-associated peritonitis. The project aims to integrate physical, biochemical, and image-based diagnostic techniques to develop a machine learning (ML) algorithm capable of identifying early changes in dialysate turbidity—prior to their visual detectability. A comprehensive dataset will be compiled during the study, and the algorithm will be validated in a clinical setting. Additionally, the potential use of bacteriophages will be explored as an alternative diagnostic and therapeutic approach, particularly in cases involving antibiotic-resistant pathogens. The project will generate a large, standardized dataset to serve as a foundation for ML model training. The proposed solutions are expected to improve early peritonitis diagnostics, enhance patient survival, reduce hospitalization duration and treatment costs, and establish a basis for the development and commercialization of new digital diagnostic tools in Latvia.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

From Cloudiness to Clarity:
Predictive Modeling for Early

Diagnosis of Peritonitis in Peritoneal Dialysis (CLEAR-PD)

Researchers

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Organizations

Pauls Stradiņš Clinical University Hospital, Institute of Electronics and Computer Science, Rīga Stradiņš University (RSU)

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [From Cloudiness to Clarity: Predictive Modeling for Early Diagnosis of Peritonitis in Peritoneal Dialysis \(CLEAR-PD\)](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grants: From Cloudiness to Clarity: Predictive Modeling for Early Diagnosis of Peritonitis in Peritoneal Dialysis (CLEAR-PD)

Project:

3. License

License:

Access Rights: Restricted

4. Templates

Descriptions

RSU DMP Template

Template: RSU DMP Template

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Purpose of data

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The proposed project aims to generate measurable academic, societal, and economic impact by advancing nephrology research, improving patient diagnostics, and encouraging healthcare innovation. It will identify early

diagnostic markers for peritoneal dialysis associated peritonitis by analyzing visual, physical, and biochemical parameters, aiming for sensitivity and specificity comparable to gold standard methods. A machine-learning (ML) algorithm will detect early signs of dialysate turbidity, leading to an ML-based model for recognizing turbidity from photographic images of used dialysate bags, providing a novel non-invasive detection method. An experimental method for determining the bacteriophage lytic spectrum will also be tested to improve pathogen identification and antibiotic selection.

1.1.2 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")?

The ML solution could power a mobile app for detecting peritonitis using patient-reported symptoms, dialysate images, and home measurements, integrated into global clinical workflows for early detection and treatment. This tool would aid patients, nurses, and physicians recognize turbidity changes, promoting earlier detection and faster treatment. The project will advance digital nephrology technologies, foster interdisciplinary collaboration, and integrate ML in healthcare. Long-term sustainability will be ensured through open-source implementation, clinical validation, and partnerships with med-tech companies. In the future, diagnostic markers may be incorporated into self-testing tools like colorimetric strips, reducing delays, promoting self-monitoring, and improving outcomes in peritoneal dialysis.

1.2 Data characteristics

1.2.1 Type of data generated/collected

- Clinical data
- Programme source code
- Machine-readable text
- Experimental data

- Observation data
- Ratings
- Other

pictures of PD fluids

1.2.2 Format of data generated/collected

- XML
- TXT
- CSV
- PNG
- JSON
- JPG

1.2.3 Expected volume of the data

The total expected volume of the data (including tabular clinical and biochemical results, clinical variables, cytokine measurements, microbiological findings, and dialysate images) is estimated to be no more than 100 GB.

1.2.4 Are you re-using this dataset?

No

The project does not reuse any existing datasets. All clinical data, laboratory measurements, physical analyses, and dialysate images (including simulated images) will be newly collected or newly generated specifically for this study.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

During the project, internal unique identifiers will be assigned to all data files and records (e.g., sequential study IDs for participants, standardized naming conventions for image files). As the dataset is not planned for public repository deposit, no external persistent identifiers (such as DOI) will be assigned at this stage. However, if a decision is made in the future to publish part of the dataset (e.g., anonymized image data or ML model outputs) in RSU Dataverse or another repository, DOIs will be automatically assigned upon publication.

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you provide clear version numbers?

No

2.1.6 Will you document the dataset?

Yes

- Codebook
- ReadMe file
- Laboratory notebook and experimental protocol
- Methodology description
- Software documentation

2.2 Data accessibility

2.2.1 Are the data formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

All data formats used in this project are open, non-proprietary, and accessible with widely used free software.

2.2.2 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Data is stored on a locally hosted NextCloud instance, accessible to authorized project team members via web browser (no software installation required), desktop client, or NextCloud mobile app. Once data is downloaded, the tabular data can be accessed by spreadsheet software (Excel, LibreOffice Calc), Python, or other text editors, the images would be accessible by any standard image viewer and Python image processing libraries.

2.2.3 Is it possible to include the relevant software in the dataset (e.g. source code)?

Yes

2.2.4 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy/ontology to make your data interoperable?

No

2.3 Data publishing and long-term preservation

2.3.2 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Other (Non-Commercial)

No open license will be applied, as the datasets large volume makes public deposition in a repository impractical. Therefore, it will not be made publicly available.

2.3.3 What type of access the dataset will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

Individualised access to the dataset is open only for project group members.

2.3.4 Will there be an embargo period for access to these data?

No

No embargo period planned

2.3.6 Will you provide reference to the dataset in scientific publications and other research outputs?

No

2.3.7 Other relevant remarks

As the dataset will not be deposited in a public repository, no dataset reference or link will be provided in scientific publications or other research outputs.

As a dataset with all dialysate pictures requires significant storage space and is not easy to review, it will not be published. There is a possibility to publish only tabular data.

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources and quality assurance

3.1.1 Which costs will be covered within this project for making data FAIR?

- Storage

- Archiving

- Security

Euro

300-1000

3.1.2 Have you discussed how the costs will be covered?

No additional costs are required.

3.1.3 Which institutions are responsible for handling the data? Which institution(s) are the data controller in this project?

- Pauls Stradiņš Clinical University Hospital
- Institute of Electronics and Computer Science
- Riga Stradiņš University

3.1.4 Who will be responsible for data management in your project? Which person will be the data manager responsible for the correct processing of data in the project, staff training, and maintenance of the data management plan?

Karlīs Racenis (orcid: [0000-0001-7123-4048](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7123-4048))

3.1.5 Who will collect and process the data for this study (name data processors-researchers, laboratory technicians, assistants, and other persons who will work with the data for this study)?

- Roberts Kadiķis (0000-0001-6845-4381)
- Karlīs Racenis (orcid: [0000-0001-7123-4048](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7123-4048))
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- Diana Duplevska (0000-0002-8766-3928)

Comment:

Project leader - Kārlis Rācenis, MD, PhD, will be responsible for clinical investigation, statistical analysis, scientific paper writing, and dissemination activities.

Anna Popova, MD, a nephrologist at PSCUH, will manage patient and control group visits, also responsible for database management, statistical analysis, scientific paper writing and dissemination activities.

Anna Jana Saulīte, resident in nephrology, is initiating her PhD within this project. Researcher will coordinate patient recruitment, clinical sample management, data collection, result integration, scientific paper writing and dissemination activities.

Dace Eglīte, MD, a resident doctor in clinical microbiology with considerable expertise and hands-on experience in identifying and analyzing microorganisms in clinical samples. Researcher will contribute to the advancement of microbial diagnostic methodologies, the application of bacteriophages, and laboratory management.

Gatis Saknītis: at RSU will support sample collection, preparation, and preliminary analysis, perform routine procedures.

Roberts Kadiķis, Dr. sc. ing., is a senior researcher at EDI. Expert in machine learning, computer vision, and generative AI - tools which he has applied on tasks and in projects on diverse topics in fields of biomedicine, industry, and mobility. He will supervise the ML-related part of the project.

Maksims Ivanovs and Diana Duplevska at EDI will implement ML algorithms and carry out their initial validation on the test data.

3.1.6 Are there data quality assurance processes foreseen?

Yes

Data will be generated and processed according to a predefined methodology, with validation and quality checks applied prior to analysis.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords

Data will be stored on a locally hosted NextCloud with restricted access limited to authorized project members. Data transmission to/from NextCloud will be protected using encrypted connections (HTTPS/TLS). Access will be controlled via individual user accounts and strong passwords. The hosting infrastructure will be protected by institutional firewalls and regular security updates.

3.2.2 What provisions are in place for data security?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

Data access: Access to research data is restricted to authorized project staff only, using individual user accounts and role-based permissions in the locally hosted NextCloud. Access rights are reviewed and updated when team membership changes.

Data storage: Data is stored on institutional infrastructure (locally hosted NextCloud) with controlled administrative access. Data is organized into project

folders with least-privilege permissions. Sensitive datasets are stored in pseudonymised form.

Data transmission: Data transfer is performed only through encrypted channels (HTTPS/TLS). No sensitive data is sent via unencrypted email or consumer file-sharing services.

Data recovery: Regular backups are maintained, and restoration procedures are available to ensure recovery in case of accidental deletion or system failure.

Data sharing: Data is shared only within the consortium via NextCloud controlled sharing (restricted links / user-to-user sharing). Any external sharing (if needed) would be based on approval by the project leader.

3.2.3 Where the data will be stored during research? For how long the data will be stored there?

The research data will be collected in a unified questionnaire that will not include personal identifiers such as name, surname, or date of birth; instead, each participant will be assigned a unique study identification number. Informed consent forms and the re-identification keys for pseudonymized data will be stored for 75 years in a separate locked cabinet of the project leaders office within the Nephrology Centre of Pauls Stradiņš Clinical University Hospital (PSCUH), accessible only to the project researchers.

Biological samples will be identifiable during the study period (3 years); after completion of the study, dialysate samples will be pseudonymised. A volume of 6–10 ml of drained dialysate will be used for the determination of peritonitis markers (e.g. CRP, COX-2, IL-2). Smaller volumes of material will be frozen and stored in the PSCUH Central Laboratory for the duration of the consent form storage period. The remaining material may subsequently be used in other PSCUH scientific studies that have obtained the required approvals in accordance with applicable regulations.

Dialysate samples will be analysed in the PSCUH Central Laboratory, and following the acquisition of results, the samples will be disposed of as biological material. Biological samples will be stored in a pseudonymised form in the laboratory for the duration of the consent form storage period.

3.2.4 When and how will data from the specified storage location be deleted or destroyed?

Electronic data will be securely deleted after the project and required retention period using certified electronic deletion methods. Physical documents will be destroyed by shredding or via certified services. All deletions will be documented and verified by an IT specialist to ensure irreversibility.

3.2.5 Have you ensured that your chosen repository is appropriate for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

Since the data will not be published, no repository will be used.

3.3 Ethical and legal aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

The ethical and legal issues are mostly related to personal data and sensitive information, but it certainly isn't limited to it.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is it planned to conduct an informed consent process for research subjects?

Yes

3.3.4 Where and for how long will the signed informed consent forms be stored?
Who will have access to these documents?

Signed informed consent forms will be stored for 75 years in a specially designated archive - separate locked cabinet of the project leaders office within the Nephrology Centre of Pauls Stradiņš Clinical University Hospital (PSCUH), accessible only to the project researchers.

3.3.5 Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data (if applicable)?

No. Informed consent does not include consent for data sharing or public re-use. It includes consent for long-term institutional storage only.

3.3.6 Will data collected/generated include personal data or any other sensitive information?

No

3.3.10 What methods do you intend to use to process and access the data securely?

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- National laws
- Pseudonymization

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